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TACTICS OF MANAGEMENT OF PREGNANT WOMEN WITH EPILEPSY (LITERARY REVIEW)

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ANNOTATION

The article presents a review of modern antiepileptic drugs and their effect on the foetus. Most antiepileptic drugs have various side effects such as craniofacial defects, skeletal anomalies, delayed physical and mental development.

Keywords: epilepsy, pregnant women, antiepileptic drugs, women

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ТАКТИКА ВЕДЕНИЯ БЕРЕМЕННЫХ ЖЕНЩИН С ЭПИЛЕПСИЕЙ (ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЙ ОБЗОР)

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье приведен обзор современных противоэpileптических препаратов и их влияние на плод. Большинство антиэpileптических препаратов обладают различными побочными эффектами, такими как краниофациальные дефекты, скелетные аномалии, задержка физического и умственного развития.

Ключевые слова: эпилепсия, беременные, противоэpileптические препараты, женщины

Asqarova Fotima Kudratovna

Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti

EPILEPSIYA BILAN HOMILADOR AYOLLARNI OLIV BORISH USLUBI (ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI)

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada zamonaviy antiepileptik dorilar va ularning homilaga ta'siri haqida umumiy ma'lumot berilgan. Aksariyat antiepileptik dorilar kraniofasiyal nuqsonlar, skelet anomalialari, jismoniy va aqliy rivojlanishning kechikishi kabi turli xil yon ta'sirga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: epilepsiya, homilador ayollar, epilepsiyaga qarshi dorilar, ayollar

Introduction. Recently, the issue of continuation of labour in women with epilepsy has become more and more acute. On average, the prevalence of epilepsy among pregnant women is 0.3-1% according to different authors. The article reviews the main approaches to the management of pregnant women with epilepsy. Pregravidar preparation includes comprehensive observation by several specialists, competent choice of anti-epileptic drug and selection of the minimum effective dose. According to the literature, switching a woman to monotherapy with antiepileptic drugs at the lowest therapeutic dose reduces the risk of pregnancy complications and congenital malformations in the foetus. In order to prevent intrauterine malformations, the use of folic acid is justified according to the recommendations of many authors. Delivery of women with epilepsy is carried out naturally in the absence of contraindications.

Epilepsy is a chronic brain disease characterised by a persistent predisposition to epileptic seizures as a result of pathological, excessive activity of synchronised extensive populations of brain neurons, leading to neurobiological, cognitive, psychological and social consequences of this condition.

In recent years, women with epilepsy are increasingly trying to realise their childbearing function. On average, the prevalence of

epilepsy among pregnant women is 0.3-1% according to different authors [4, 5]. In the USA, every 3-5 children per 1,000 newborns are born to a mother with epilepsy. In total, there are about 1.5 million women of childbearing age with this pathology [12]. In Turkey, pregnant women with epilepsy account for 1.65% of pregnant women with epilepsy [7]. A study conducted in Nigeria from 2022-2023 identified 3.33 pregnant women with epilepsy per 1,000 population (95% CI 2.1-4.8) [25]. In India, there are 2.5 million women with epilepsy, 52% of whom are in their reproductive years [6]. Given these statistics, more information is becoming available every year on the preparation of such patients for pregnancy, management of labour and postpartum period. Women with extragenital pathology constitute a special group of increased control during pregnancy, which is directly related to risks for maternal and foetal health. Epilepsy alarms physicians with its spontaneity and difficulty in controlling seizures. The impact of pregnancy on the course of epilepsy is individualised. Based on data from numerous studies, the increase in seizure frequency and the number of complications of epilepsy occurring during pregnancy are not statistically significant or consistent.

The follow-up of such women should be comprehensive - under the supervision of a neurologist, obstetrician-gynaecologist, geneticist and,

if possible, an epileptologist. Pregravida preparation is an important component of a favourable pregnancy outcome. Summarising data from various guidelines for the management of pregnant women with epilepsy, we can highlight the main principles: a) choose the optimal treatment option before conception; b) monotherapy is preferable, if possible; c) choose the most effective antiepileptic drug (AED) depending on the type and frequency of seizures; d) start therapy with the lowest effective dose (in case of epilepsy debut during pregnancy); e) prevention of birth defects - folic acid intake [9].

Pregnancy planning is contraindicated if the patient has intractable epilepsy with frequent generalised seizures, status epilepticus, and/or severe personality changes that pose a threat to the health and life of both mother and foetus [1]. However, it should be noted that contraindications to pregnancy are relative, and if a woman decides to become pregnant, even in cases of uncompensated disease and severe personality changes, the pregnancy is terminated only at the patient's discretion.

Preparing a patient with epilepsy for pregnancy begins with the selection of the drug and the minimum therapeutic dose. Monotherapy with second-generation drugs is the most appropriate approach, as they have a good effect, are less toxic, and have a low-risk category (FDA C) for congenital malformations [12]. According to the UK regulatory authorities, polytherapy has a congenital malformation rate of up to 6%, while monotherapy and no AED therapy have rates of 3.7 and 3.5%, respectively [5]. Antenatal exposure to AEDs significantly increases the risk of fetal congenital malformations (FCD) from a background level of 1-2% in healthy women to 4-9% in women with epilepsy [3]. In the general population, the average risk of congenital malformations is 16.3% [5]. AEDs, according to the FDA classification of fetal risk categories, occupy 3 categories: C - risk not excluded, D - risk proven and X - contraindicated in pregnancy. Category C drugs are representatives of the second generation of AEDs: lamotrigine, ethosuximide, levetiracetam, oxcarbazepine, lacosamide, zonisamide, perampanel, tiagabine.

These drugs do not have teratogenic effects, but may cause various developmental defects, such as intrauterine developmental delay, cardiovascular malformations (ventricular septal defect, valve anomalies), visceral anomalies (perampanel), delayed ossification (lamotrigine) and others. A dose-dependent effect of fetal anomalies was observed with lamotrigine in a study conducted in the UK. In treatment with first-generation AEDs (valproic acid, carbamazepine, phenobarbital, clonazepam), more severe birth defects and malformations were observed in the form of cleft palate, craniofacial defects, skeletal anomalies, coagulation defects, and neural tube development defects.

Congenital spina bifida malformation is associated with carbamazepine monotherapy.

Based on available data, the safest AEDs in pregnancy are levetiracetam and lamotrigine, followed by carbamazepine and oxcarbazepine; then phenytoin, phenobarbital, topiramate and the least safe valproic acid. The European and International Register of Antiepileptic Drugs and Pregnancy (EURAP) has confirmed that, in addition to the type of AED, the risk of major congenital malformations is also influenced by the dose of the drug at the time of conception.

Valproate has a good effect in the treatment of epilepsy, but its use in pregnancy has serious consequences. Valproates cause neural tube defects, structural anomalies of the facial skull, cardiovascular malformations, hypospadias, limb malformations, haemodynamic disorders. The risk of foetal malformations with valproic acid is 10.73%, the highest percentage compared to other drugs [6]. The use of valproic acid in women of childbearing age is justified when all possible risks are assessed, when there is remission on the background of valproic acid monotherapy, and when seizures, especially generalised convulsive seizures, are more dangerous for the mother and foetus than the teratogenic effect of AEDs. Breastfeeding is usually not contraindicated, as valproic acid penetrates into milk minimally (up to 10%), but the condition of the child should be taken into account. The ideal option for prescribing valproic acid in young women of fertile age is as monotherapy, using the lowest effective daily dose and prolonged forms [1].

According to the UK National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence (NICE) 2012, a relatively safe dose of valproic acid in pregnancy is considered to be 800 mg/day; data on the possibility of using valproic acid at a dose of up to 1,000 mg/day have also been published [10]. When two AEDs are administered, neither of which is valproic acid, the risk of congenital malformations is markedly reduced: 9.1% of birth defects with lamotrigine therapy with valproic acid (OR 5.0; 95% CI 1.5-14.0), but only 2.9% of lamotrigine with other AEDs (OR 1.5; 95% CI 0.7-3.0); in addition, the risk is 15.4% for carbamazepine with valproic acid (OR 6.2; 95% CI 2.0-16.5) and 2.5% for carbamazepine plus any other AED (OR 0.8; 95% CI 0.3-1.9) [1,6].

Studies assessing child development before school suggest that up to 30-40% of children whose mothers took valproic acid during pregnancy start walking and talking later, have lower intellectual abilities and problems with expressive and impression speech and memory [8].

Carbamazepine use during pregnancy increases the risk of the following defects: facial skull anomalies, microcephaly, neural tube defects, cardiovascular malformations, neonatal seizures, and low IQ [20]. The prevalence of these defects varies between 3,34,93% among children whose mothers were taking carbamazepine in monotherapy or in combination with other AEDs [1]. But compared to the use of valproic acid, malformations associated with carbamazepine treatment are less common. In the study of J. Jentink determined specific defects occurring when carbamazepine is administered to pregnant women with epilepsy. According to the data, the occurrence of spina bifida in the general population and maternal carbamazepine intake corresponds to 2.6 (95% CI 1.2-5.3) and 4.2 (95% CI 1.5-11.2), the risk of other defects differs insignificantly [8].

Infants exposed to phenobarbital intrauterine have been reported to develop fetal hydantoin syndrome (craniofacial anomalies, growth deficiency, underdevelopment of finger and toe nails, and/or mild developmental delay, harelip and wolf's mouth, microcephaly, brain malformations), as well as symptoms characteristic of fetal alcohol syndrome. Most studies have not investigated or reported a potential relationship between phenobarbital dose and the risk of malformations [7].

However, EURAP found an increased incidence of malformations in children exposed to phenobarbital (5.4% for doses <150 mg/day vs. 13.7% for doses >150 mg/day) [8]. The mechanism of the AED dose effect is not completely clear but is considered a possible risk factor. Multiple assessments of the mental development of children intrauterine exposed to phenobarbital monotherapy found no differences with children in the control group [9].

Folic acid supplementation before conception and in the first 3 months of pregnancy reduces the risk of neural tube defect [7]. In a study by S. Hernandez-Diaz et al. with a case-control design showed that taking folic acid antagonists, such as carbamazepine, phenobarbital, phenytoin, increases the risk of predominantly neural tube defect. Two groups of children were compared: those with a proven neural tube defect (n=1,242) and those with malformations other than neural tube defect (n=6,660, control group). In group I, administration of any folic acid antagonists was recorded in 2.2% of cases, with carbamazepine being the most common (0.5%), while in the control group it was recorded in 1 and 0.1% of cases, respectively. The results of the study demonstrate the specificity of the teratogenic effect of folic acid antagonists and indicate a selective protective effect of folic acid against neural tube malformations [4]. The increased requirement for folic acid during pregnancy when taking AEDs is associated with the competitive effect of AEDs and folic acid on the liver microsomal system [3]. The combination of mutations in genes encoding enzymatic reactions of the folate cycle with AED administration leads to an increased risk of foetal CHD [9].

The American Academy of Neurology recommends the use of folic acid before conception and during pregnancy at a dose of 0.4 mg/day, and up to 4 mg/day in the case of aggravated heredity for spinal cord birth defects to prevent fetal macroanomalies [2].

Electroencephalographic (EEG) study and determination of AEP concentration is carried out in compensated epilepsy once every 2 months or less frequently, in case of observed seizures - at every visit of

a pregnant woman to a neurologist. Concentrations of hormones of the foeto-placental complex (placental actogen, progesterone, estriol, cortisone) and a-fetoprotein are examined starting from the end of the first trimester of pregnancy and subsequently at least once a month. In compensated epilepsy there are no peculiarities in prenatal preparation, delivery is a physiological decision. Indications for early delivery are as follows

CONCLUSIONS. 1 Patients with epilepsy should plan pregnancy in advance in order to prevent complications. It is recommended to take second-generation AEDs (lamotrigine, kep-pra) during pregnancy.

2. Monotherapy with AEDs at a dose calculated on the basis of the drug concentration in serum is recommended. 3.

3. EEG monitoring is necessary once every 3 months in unstable course of epilepsy.

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